

Condensation of Dibenzylketone with Aromatic

Aldehydes and Ketones

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Goldschmiedt and Knöpfer (*Monatsh.*, 1898, 19, 406), Hertzka (*Monatsh.*, 1905, 26, 227) and Schimetschek (*Monatsh.*, 1906, 27, 1) studied the condensations of dibenzylketone with different aromatic aldehydes in presence of dry hydrochloric acid gas in ice-cold benzene solution and got in each case the hydrogen chloride additive product of the benzylidenedibenzylketone, which on heating, decomposed in most cases and only in a few cases gave off hydrochloric acid yielding the unsaturated product. Goldschmiedt and Spitzauer (*Monatsh.*, 1903, 24, 270) isolated benzylidenedibenzylketone by the action of strong alcoholic solution of caustic potash on the hydrochloride. Goldschmiedt and Knöpfer (*Monatsh.*, 1899, 20, 734) using dilute potassium hydroxide obtained an addition product of two molecules of benzaldehyde with one molecule of dibenzylketone. In the present investigation the condensation of dibenzylketone with aromatic aldehydes and ketones have been further investigated by using at ordinary temperature (i) 60 p.c. alcoholic caustic potash solution and (ii) dry hydrochloric acid gas and very satisfactory results have been obtained.

Benzaldehyde, *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde and cinnamic aldehyde in methyl alcoholic solution condense readily at ordinary temperature with dibenzylketone in presence of 60 p.c. alcoholic potassium hydroxide; one molecule of the ketone condensing with one molecule of the aldehyde, forming the benzylidene derivatives in good yields. It is interesting to note that dibenzylketone reacts with two molecules of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde under conditions in which it reacts with only one molecule of benzaldehyde or cinnamic aldehyde.

Cinnamylidenedibenzylketone, m.p. 110°, reacts in an interesting manner with two molecules of hydroxylamine, which can be satisfactorily explained by Thiele's theory of conjugated double bonds—

The hydroxyaldehydes, *e.g.*, salicylaldehyde, resorcyaldehyde and *o*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, which appear not to react readily in presence of 60 p.c. alcoholic potash solution, have been successfully condensed with dibenzylketone in presence of dry hydrochloric acid gas at the ordinary temperature. The salicylaldehyde compound is completely insoluble in caustic alkali, even on boiling, which shows that the hydroxyl group takes part in the reaction, yielding product (I) or (II)

(I)

(II)

But as the condensation product gives a hydrazone (m.p. 50°) the formula (I) is the most probable one; it is however remarkable that it behaves in the ketonic and not in the enolic form. The resorcyaldehyde compound yields a monobenzoyl derivative (m.p. 110°), and a hydrazone (m.p. 104°); hence it may be given the following structure:

The condensation product of *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde with dibenzylketone is deep violet, readily soluble in caustic alkali and giving a

dibenzoyl derivative (m.p. 158°), a hydrazone (m.p. 120°) and an oxime (m.p. 131-33°): it may therefore be represented thus:

It may be observed in this connection that chloro-*p*-hydroxybenzyl-dibenzylketone was obtained by Schimetschek (*loc. cit.*) by the action of hydrochloric acid on a mixture of dibenzylketone and *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde dissolved in acetic acid; only one molecule of the aldehyde condensed with one molecule of dibenzylketone.

m-Hydroxybenzaldehyde under similar conditions condensed with dibenzylketone yielding two products insoluble in caustic alkali; one, soluble in ether melting at 114-16° and the other sparingly soluble in ether and does not melt up to 240°. These have not been further investigated.

The condensation of dibenzylketone with ketones appears not to have been studied much before. Henderson and Corstorphine (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, 79, 1256) by heating a mixture of dibenzylketone and benzil for a short time on the water-bath with 33 p.c. aqueous potassium hydroxide, obtained tetraphenylcyclopentenolone.

Dibenzylketone has now been condensed with typical ketones such as acetone, acetophenone, benzophenone, by using 60 p.c. alcoholic caustic potash solution, one molecule of dibenzylketone readily condensing with two molecules of the ketone with a good yield.

The diketones, isatin and phenathraquinone, have also been condensed with dibenzylketone by the action of 60 p. c. alcoholic caustic potash solution, and compounds, similar to the condensation product of benzil with dibenzylketone of Henderson and Corstorphine (*loc. cit.*), have been obtained.

The light yellow condensation product of isatin and dibenzylketone melts at 255° - 57° , and is soluble in caustic alkali. The compound gives a dibromide, which does not melt up to 270° . The structure of the compound is

It gives a perfectly white oxime, which does not melt even when heated up to 280°

The phenanthraquinone condensation product is soluble in caustic alkali on heating and like cinnamylidenedibenzylketone reacts with two molecules of hydroxylamine.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Benzylidenedibenzylketone.—Dibenzylketone (2.1 g.) and benzaldehyde (1.06 g.) are dissolved in methyl alcohol (15 c.c.) and a few drops of 60 p.c. alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution are added. After three hours the mixture is poured into water and the precipitate thoroughly washed with hot water and crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless microcrystalline powder, m.p. 86° . It is identical with the compound isolated by Goldschmiedt and Spitzauer (*loc. cit.*), yield 75 p.c. It is soluble in alcohol, acetone, ether, benzene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and nitrobenzene. (Found: C, 88.52; 88.5; H, 5.99. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}$ requires C, 88.59; H, 6.04 per cent.)

The phenylhydrazone crystallises from dilute alcohol as a microcrystalline powder, m.p. 90 - 91° . (Found: N, 7.19, 7.08. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_2$ requires N, 7.21 per cent.)

Cinnamylidenedibenzylketone is prepared from dibenzylketone (3.15 g.), cinnamic aldehyde (dissolved in methyl alcohol 15 c.c.) with a few drops of 60 p.c. alcoholic caustic potash solution. After two hours the mixture is poured into water and the yellow precipitate washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol as a microcrystalline powder melting at 110°, yield 79 p.c. It is soluble in alcohol, acetone, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene, ether, nitrobenzene and glacial acetic acid. (Found: C, 88.76, 88.72; H, 6.15, 6.09. $C_{24}H_{20}O$ requires C, 88.38; H, 6.17 per cent.).

The hydrazone, prepared as usual, crystallises from dilute alcohol as a chocolate-coloured microcrystalline powder melting at 120°. (Found: N, 6.73. $C_{30}H_{26}N_2$ requires N, 6.76 per cent.).

The oxime, obtained as a yellow powder, melts at 150-51°. (Found: N, 7.48, 7.41. $C_{24}H_{24}O_2N_2$ requires N, 7.52 per cent.).

Di-ortho-nitrobenzylidenedibenzylketone is prepared by the condensation of 2 molecules of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde and one molecule of dibenzylketone with a few drops of 60 p.c. alcoholic caustic potash solution. It is crystallised from alcohol as small orange-red needles, which become brick-red at 215° and melt at 226°. It is soluble in acetone alcohol, benzene, ether, chloroform and carbon tetrachloride. (Found: N, 5.80, 5.75. $C_{29}H_{20}N_2O_5$ requires N, 5.88 per cent.).

The phenylhydrazone, prepared in the usual manner, is obtained as a microcrystalline powder melting at 100°. (Found: N, 9.74, 9.68. $C_{35}H_{26}O_4N_4$ requires N, 9.89 per cent.).

Condensation product of Salicylaldehyde and Dibenzylketone.—

Dry hydrochloric acid gas is passed for an hour and a half at ordinary temperature into a solution of dibenzylketone (3.15 g.) and salicylaldehyde (1.83 g.) in methyl alcohol (20 c.c.), when a yellow solid separates out. The mixture is then poured into water and the solid is powdered and washed with dilute caustic soda solution. It is obtained as a microcrystalline powder melting at 106° from dilute alcohol. It is soluble in alcohol, acetone, benzene, nitrobenzene, ether and chloroform. (Found: C, 88.89, 89.09; H, 5.39, 5.39. $C_{22}H_{16}O$ requires C, 89.18; H, 5.40 per cent.).

The phenylhydrazone is obtained as fine powder melting at 50° from dilute alcohol. (Found: N, 7.12, 7.17. $C_{28}H_{22}N_2$ requires N, 7.25 per cent.).

Condensation product of Resorcyaldehyde and Dibenzylketone.— It is obtained as in the case of salicylaldehyde. The brown mass is dissolved in caustic alkali solution, precipitated with acid, an

obtained as brick-red powder melting at 151-52° from dilute alcohol. It is soluble in alcohol, acetone, chloroform, benzene, nitrobenzene, ether. and caustic alkali. (Found: C, 84.45, 84.47; H, 5.08, 5.08. $C_{22}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 84.61; H, 5.12 per cent.).

The *phenylhydrazone*, is obtained as a red microcrystalline powder melting at 104-05° from dilute alcohol. (Found: N, 6.79. $C_{28}H_{22}ON_2$ requires N, 6.96 per cent.).

The *benzoyl* derivative, prepared by Schotten-Baumann process, is obtained as a microcrystalline powder melting at 110-11° from alcohol. (Found: C, 83.48, 83.47; H, 4.79. $C_{29}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 83.65; H, 4.8 per cent.).

Di-p-hydroxydibenzylidenedibenzylketone is prepared by passing dry hydrochloric acid gas at ordinary temperature to a mixture of dibenzylketone (2.1 g.), *para*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (2.5 g.), dissolved in methyl alcohol (15 c.c.) when a deep violet semi-solid mass is obtained. The whole mass solidifies on the addition of a little water. It is powdered, washed with carbon tetrachloride and hot water and obtained from dilute alcohol as deep violet microcrystalline powder melting at 170°. (Found: C, 83.16; H, 5.19. $C_{29}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 83.25; H, 5.26 per cent.).

The *phenyl hydrazone* is obtained as a microcrystalline yellow powder melting at 120-22° from dilute alcohol. (Found: N, 4.99. $C_{35}H_{28}O_2N_2$ requires N, 5.51 per cent.).

The oxime crystallises from dilute alcohol and is obtained as a microcrystalline powder melting at 131°. (Found: N, 3.08. $C_{29}H_{27}O_3N$ requires N, 3.23 per cent.).

The *dibenzoyl* derivative, crystallises from dilute acetone and is obtained as a microcrystalline powder melting at 158°. (Found: C, 82.29; H, 4.79. $C_{43}H_{30}O_5$ requires C, 82.42; H, 4.79 per cent.).

Bis-isopropylidenedibenzylketone.—A few drops of 60 p. c. alcoholic caustic potash solution are added to a mixture of dibenzylketone (3.15 g.) and acetone (1.87 g.) dissolved in alcohol (14 c.c.). After four hours the solution is poured into acidified water and the yellow precipitate washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol as

a powder melting at 91-92°. (Found: C, 86.78; H, 7.49. $C_{21}H_{22}O$ requires C, 86.89; H, 7.58 per cent.).

The *phenylhydrazone* is obtained as a chocolate coloured microcrystalline powder melting at 99° from dilute alcohol. (Found: N, 7.13. $C_{27}H_{28}N_2$ requires N, 7.36 per cent.).

The *oxime* crystallises from dilute alcohol as a light brown microcrystalline powder melting at 102°. (Found: N, 4.51. $C_{21}H_{23}ON$ requires N, 4.58 per cent.).

Bis-phenylethylidenedibenzylketone is prepared from dibenzylketone and acetophenone in the same manner as with acetone. The pasty mass, obtained on pouring the mixture into water, is extracted with carbon tetrachloride and the semi-solid left on removing the solvent is alternately dissolved in alcohol and acetone and poured into water, when a yellow precipitate is obtained. It is finally obtained as a microcrystalline powder from dilute alcohol melting at 95°. (Found: C, 89.71; H, 6.08. $C_{31}H_{26}O$ requires C, 89.85; H, 6.18 per cent.).

The *phenyl hydrazone* is obtained as a brown powder melting at 106-07° from dilute alcohol. (Found: N, 5.50. $C_{37}H_{32}N_2$ requires N, 5.55 per cent.).

Bis-phenylbenzylidenedibenzylketone is prepared from dibenzylketone and benzophenone. The method of preparation and purification is the same as in the case of acetophenone; yellow microcrystalline powder, m.p. 91-92°. (Found: C, 91.38; H, 5.49. $C_{41}H_{36}O$ requires C, 91.44; H, 5.49 per cent.).

Condensation product of Isatin and Dibenzylketone.—To a solution of dibenzylketone (4.2 g.) and isatin (3 g.), in alcohol (40 c. c.), a few drops of 60 p. c. alcoholic caustic potash solution are added and after three hours the solution is poured into water and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, when a light yellow precipitate is obtained. It is washed with hot water and obtained as a light yellow microcrystalline powder melting at 255-57°. It is soluble in pyridine, nitrobenzene, glacial acetic acid and caustic alkali and sparingly in alcohol, acetone and chloroform. (Found: N, 3.93. $C_{23}H_{16}O_2N$ requires N, 4.14 per cent.).

The *oxime* is colourless and does not melt when heated up to 280°. (Found: N, 7.46. $C_{23}H_{18}O_2N_2$ requires N, 7.90 per cent.).

The *dibromide*, obtained by adding bromine water to the pyridine solution of the compound, is obtained as a grey crystalline powder from dilute acetone. It does not melt when heated up to 270°.

(Found: Br, 31.80, 31.41. $C_{23}H_{17}O_2NBr_2$ requires Br, 32.06 per cent.).

Condensation product of Dibenzylketone with Phenanthraquinone.—Dibenzylketone (5.1 g.), phenanthraquinone (2.08 g.) are dissolved in benzene (50 c. c.) and a few drops of 60 p. c. alcoholic caustic potash are added. After five hours, the benzene is driven off, the solid is dissolved in alcohol and the solution poured in acidified water, when a yellow compound is obtained. It is finally crystallised from dilute alcohol and obtained as a yellow microcrystalline powder, which turns brown at 84° and melts at $102-103^\circ$. It is soluble in alcohol, acetone, benzene, chloroform carbontetrachloride, ether and sparingly soluble in caustic alkali on boiling. (Found: C, 86.60, H, 4.88. $C_{29}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 87.00; H, 5.00 per cent.).

The oxime is obtained as a microcrystalline powder melting at 98° from dilute alcohol. (Found: N, 6.06. $C_{29}H_{24}O_3N_2$ requires N, 6.25 per cent.).

The hydrazone crystallises from dilute alcohol and is obtained as a crystalline powder melting at 80° . (Found: N, 5.51. $C_{35}H_{26}ON_2$ requires N, 5.71 per cent.).

The dibromide, obtained by adding bromine to the compound, dissolved in chloroform, crystallises from dilute acetone as small orange-red prisms melting at $148-50^\circ$. (Found: Br, 38.36. $C_{29}H_{20}O_2 Br_2$ requires Br, 28.57 per cent.).